

To what extent do Brazilian NGOs in the state of Pará choose their organisation/ project locations based on assessed need?¹

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Submetido em: 28/11/2022

Aprovado em: 29/11/2022

Publicado em: 09/12/2022

DOI: 10.51473/rcmos.v2i2.443

Abstract

Following democratizing reforms and the introduction of new legislation in the late 1990s, NGOs in Brazil underwent a series of shifts regarding their funding and relationship with the government. In this context, this research project investigates the motivations for location choice of NGOs in the Brazilian state of Pará using a theoretical framework consisting of three theories. While the research project aims primarily to investigate to what extent the needs-based hypothesis applies, it will also engage with the self-interest motivation and the political connectivity motivation. Based on a mixed methods research methodology consisting of a regression analysis and multiple semi-structured interviews with NGO directors, this research comes to the conclusion that there is little quantitative evidence for clustering based on need on a national level, but finds an NGO sector reporting a very high commitment to the need-based hypothesis which is arguably not realized due to extensive funding and infrastructure constraints and an inability to account for duplication efforts. While the overall relationship between NGOs and the public sector is fraught, personal relationships and boundary-crossing are perceived as advantageous for gaining access to funding, though more explicit forms of rent-seeking behaviour are not reported.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my academic mentor Diana Weinhold for her patience and valuable feedback, David Lewis for helping me navigate a new area of research with his expertise and Jean-Paul Faguet for giving much-needed guidance. I would also like to thank all my interviewees for taking the time to share their experiences, without which this research project could not have come to fruition. Special thanks to Daman Sethi for continued moral support and encouragement.

1 Introduction

This research examines to what extent NGOs in the North of Brazil choose the location of their organization/projects based on the level of perceived need for their services by the target community. While non-profit organisations have always played an integral role in the Brazilian society, this role underwent an important reformulation with law 9790/1999, which created the Public Interest Civil Society Organization (OSCIP) certification process. This allowed NGOs to receive government transfers to finance their activities by undergoing an accreditation process and abiding by numerous periodic disclosure and evaluation requirements by local, state and national government bodies. In the years since the passage of law 9.790/1999, shifts in international funding priorities have meant that Brazilian NGOs generally and Northern NGOs specifically have faced significant funding constrains. Considering that funding is an important factor in terms of affecting an NGOs ability to locate in places of greater need, this study purports to investigate to what extent NGOs in the Pará State are effectively clustering based on need and what factors, if any, make it difficult for them to effectively target need.

¹ Artigo apresentado - MSc in Development Management 2021. Dissertation submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the degree

Despite referring to these organisations as NGOs in a broad sense, this study contemplates both special interest associations, organizations classified as OSCIPs and charitable organisations in general, investigating whether the existing selection mechanisms make them settle in environments that need their services. The existing literature on NGOs clustering identifies three main motivations for NGOs to go where they go: A community's level of need for the service provided; (2) how convenient the location is for NGO staff and founders; and (3) the political environment for NGOs operating in the country (MacLean 2015). The purpose of this study is therefore to validate the relevance of the need-based hypothesis for the clustering process of non-profits in the North of Brazil as well as exploring the relative significance of the convenience and political connectivity-based hypotheses for the experience of non-profit managers. The study uses a mixed-methods research methodology consisting of a regression analysis and semi-structured interviews. The purpose of the quantitative element will be to test the need-based hypothesis by regressing the quantity of sector-specific NGOs per municipality on the municipal performance indexes associated with the NGO activity (health, education and environmental conservation). To test the validity of the two remaining theories, semi-structured interviews with NGO managers in the Pará state will be carried out.

The results suggest little evidence for a need-based clustering process based on quantitative analysis. On the other hand, the qualitative analysis suggests that most organisations view their clustering process as predominantly needs-based, even though they acknowledge the resource constraints, infrastructure issues and labour market limitations as influencing their activities. In this way, the findings of the dissertation are in line with Jammulamadaka & Varman (2010), who find that NGOs want to cluster based on need, but often must settle for sub-optimal solutions due to a variety of impediments. This study also finds that, even if NGO would be able to cluster based on observed need for their services, they are largely neglecting to engage with each other, which can have the unintended effect of creating duplication effects that render their activities ineffective. As for the relevance of the political connectivity motivation, it can be said that, while Northern NGOs might seek out and benefit from contacts with politicians, there is little enthusiasm within the sector regarding the promise of dealing with the government. While this research points towards the possibility that the potential for rent-seeking behaviour in interactions with the state might be overestimated by organisations that do not have a funding relationship with the government, those organisations that have experience with it tend to emphasise a bureaucratic framework that ensures accountability by both the state and the NGO. Thus, the current state of NGO/state relationships in the Pará State confirms earlier, nationwide findings by Lopez et. al (2011), who argue that clientelist relationships between the public and non-profit sectors is a thing of the past.

Finally, -given the socio-political and institutional similarities between Latin American countries, the findings of this study can advance the NGO clustering literature in Latin America. There is a lack of such study/ research in the broader Latin American region. Furthermore, it is important to consider the implications of NGO clustering behaviours within the wider context of NGO-state relationships because *“knowing where NGOs locate can help policymakers and donors understand how NGOs work, who they target, and what their priorities are as organizations”* (Fruttero and Gauri, 2005, p. 761). By examining critically to what extent NGOs are capable of providing effective solutions to developmental problems, policymakers can decide whether they wish to enact legislation that either strengthens the position of the third sector as an executor of state services or restores service provision responsibilities to the state and civic engagement responsibilities to NGOs.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Contextualising the clustering literature within wider NGO research and shifting paradigms about the role of NGOs in society

Before examining the literature on NGO clustering (i.e why NGOs go where they go), it is important to briefly discuss some of the main papers in the NGO literature, which outline the historical shifts in the sector and suggest that, despite having grown in numbers and funding, there are serious doubts in terms of the ability of NGOs to deliver transformative societal change.

While civil society organisations have existed at various points in history, NGOs as we understand them today became more significant in a context of rapid globalisation, market-liberalising reforms, structural adjustment programs (SAPs) and cutbacks to public spending in the 80s and 90s (Herzer & Nunnenkamp, 2013). The initial popularity of NGO aid programs is explained at least in part due to negative sentiments regarding official aid programs at the time (Riddell & Robinson 1995). During this period, NGOs were viewed as being capable of both aligning with recipient needs better than the state and advancing democracy by boosting civil society through public participation (Koch et.al, 2009; Bratton, 1989). With financial flows from both private and public entities pouring into these non-state actors, NGO numbers in OECD countries almost doubled in this period (Smillie & Helmich, 1993).

In this context of the changing roles of NGOs in society, the merits of the third sector have been re-examined. To begin with, multiple authors have put forth the view that democracy-promoting quality of NGOs depends heavily on country context and that homogenization of NGOs means that democratisation did not lead to improved governance and representation (Banks, Hulme & Edwards, 2015; Clarke, 1998). Other authors have criticised NGOs as having become de-radicalised, de-politicised and excessively focused on private-sector development solutions (Lewis, 2017).

They have also been criticised for prioritising accountability demands of governments and donors, thereby forgoing their accountability to recipient communities (Kilby, 2006). At the same time, upwards accountability can become an operational hindrance for politically exposed organisations (Yasmin & Ghafran, 2019). These conflicting accountability demands have arguably affected their ability to effectively mobilise communities: Bano (2008) finds that NGOs are less able to evoke trust and mobilise communities than voluntary organisations. Others argue that NGOs have weak community roots, excessive focus on service delivery and forgo radical positions in favour of operational efficiency, policy influence and donor requirements (Kilby, 2006; Choudry & Kapoor 2013). Thus, Banks, Hulme & Edwards (2015) argue that NGOs have not succeeded in promoting transformative change to combat hegemonic interests because they lack the urgency, foresight and courage to move out of their comfort zone. Mercer (2002) voices similar concerns, arguing that the standard discourse of NGOs being beneficial for the bolstering of civil society and enhancing state legitimacy through a democratising role is based on ideology and not evidence.

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These criticisms of the overall aid architecture serve as an important contextualisation for this research project. The question of whether NGOs are capable of clustering in a way to target areas/environments most in need is especially important when placed within a public policy debate about the merits of funnelling international aid, private and public sector funds into NGOs

2.2 Latin American and Brazil-specific research

2.2.1 Background Information on the legal definition of an OSCIP and identification of research gaps

Before painting a broad picture of the main scholarly findings related to NGOs in Latin America generally and in Brazil specifically, this section will outline some of the legal shifts that have shaped the NGO sector in the last 30 years. For context, Brazil underwent a period of military dictatorship that began in 1964 and ended in 1986 with the promulgation of the new constitution of 1988 and the first presidential election by popular vote in 1990. During the military dictatorship, the third sector was instrumental in advancing the redemocratisation agenda, mainly relying on international multilateral funding to do so (Mendonca, Aquino and Nogueira, 2016). In 1999, the Brazilian government enacted Law 9790/99 (New Third Sector Law) with the purpose of “bringing NGOs into the fold” (Alves and Koga, 2005, p. 218). This new legal framework intended to give civil society organisations the ability to execute more comprehensive partnerships with the state by facilitating their accreditation and creating guidelines for the transfer of government funds to non-profits (ibid, p. 220). The law also created a number of new legal entities, the most relevant of which is the Public Interest Civil Society Organisation (OSCIP). After acquiring an OSCIP certification and undergoing a strict selection process, an organisation can enter a type of contract called a “letter of partnership” whereby it receives funding to execute, in its own installations, public services that are not exclusive to the state (Zanella di Pietro, 2016 as quoted in Kuser, 2009). OSCIPs must then abide by a number of disclosure requirements to continue receiving funding (Campos et. al, 2011). It is also worth noting here that, despite the many changes introduced by the sector’s legislation, there is no official legal definition of an NGO in Brazilian law, therefore not allowing this research project to place Brazilian third sector organisations within the international scholarly debate regarding the differences between non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and civil society organisations (CSOs) (Banks, Hulme & Edwards, 2015; Bano, 2008; Pousadela & Cruz, 2016).

2.2.2 Previous NGO research in Latin America

Previous Ngo-related research in Latin America generally and Brazil specifically has identified a broadly similar trends in terms of the deradicalization of NGOs in the context of democratisation and shifting aid fluxes. Foweraker (2001) finds that Latin American NGOs have undergone depolitistion and deradicalisation in the context of redemocratisation reforms. Initially, NGOs were protagonists of the structural changes brought about by redemocratisation, a co-opting process by the state, a reduction of international aid flows and the arrival of the private sector as a funding source lead to a gradual abandonment of more critical positions, adoption of universalist causes and a shift to a project-based service-provision rationale (Fratz,1987; Clarke, 1998; Da Gloria Ghon, 2013; Mendonca, Aquino and Nogueira, 2016). Pousadela and Cruz (2016) argue that this “abandonment” by international agencies (which are now predominantly targeting governments directly) has caused Latin American NGOs to abandon their advocacy work by either becoming executors of state services or relegating the non-market portion of their services.

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Brazil-specific research on accountability concerns, issues with international aid and the ability of NGOs to honor a commitment to the participatory approach also mirrors global findings. Campos et. al (2011) find that Brazilian NGOs demonstrate strongest accountability towards their donors and are not as accountable to their communities. Meanwhile, Chagas et. Al (2020) find significant gaps in terms of the legal accountability demands and what is actually enshrined into law given that 73% of North-eastern OSCIP financial statements

are not in accordance with the legislation.

While Jupp (2012) discusses experiences of Brazilian NGOs with participatory approaches, Koslinski and Reis (2009) found that Brazilian NGOs that receive foreign transfers tend to be less domestically integrated and less participatory. Much of the remaining literature studying OSCIPs in Brazil raises issues of compliance with legal, accounting, disclosure and performance measurements in a given municipality/ state (Peci et.al 2008; de Lima Pereira et. al 2015; Furtado, Giacomelli and Pacheco 2019; Chagas et. al 2020). Other studies discuss the effect that certain changes in the legislation had on aspects of NGO performance and accountability across time (Peixinho 2017; Alves and Koga 2006).

While no Latin American and Brazilian studies dealing with the issue of NGO clustering were identified directly, some studies end up addressing factors that influence location choice. As discussed by Graciliano et. al (2010), it was found that there were clear cases of conflicts of interests in OSCIP partnership contracts when OSCIP staff were also employed by a government body. This “boundary-crossing” between the private and public sector has been identified by Lewis (2008) as a relevant indicator of political relationships between NGOs and the state that might affect NGO location choice. De Lima Pereira et. al (2015), in turn, find that 73% of Brazilian NGOs surveyed reported resource mobilisation as their chief concern. When taken together with an extensive body of literature that identifies NGOs as locating in areas with greater resource mobilisation potential, the fact that NGOs in Brazil experience significant resource constraints could impact their willingness and ability to choose NGO location based primarily on the assessed community need. Lastly, while the research of Lopes, Leao and Grangeia (2011) on the relevance of clientelistic relationships between non-profits and the state is the most conceptually-similar to this research, it does not concern itself with the issue of administrative clustering in general, which is the focal point of analysis in this research.

Furthermore, if relationships with government might influence NGO location, the effectiveness of the oversight mechanisms enacted might also influence the extent to which NGOs will cluster with rent-seeking motivations. In this context, Bronstein et.al (2017) find that the municipal councils that are tasked with overseeing OSCIP activities fail to adequately embody the participatory ethos with which they were originally created.

2.3 Clustering Literature

2.3.1 Private sector research on clustering behaviours

Literature from outside the NGO field shows the relevance of geographical proximity of firms in certain contexts: According to Pinch & Sunley (2016) clusters are proximate groups of collaborating and competing firms that have multiple benefits, including lower cost, raised productivity, diffusion of knowledge and collective learning. Evidence from the USA, Switzerland and the United Kingdom suggests that a majority of venture capital investments are made in locations closer to the VC firm. (Harrison, 2003; Makela 2003; Mason & Harrison 2002). However, later research by Corrado et.al (2005), Griffith et. al (2006) and Owen-Smith & Powell (2004) suggests that, as technology reduces costs related to distance, there is a decline in the relevance of location for investment. It is suggested that the importance of spatial clustering for VC investment is higher in countries with a more centralised spatial structure like the UK and USA, while it loses relevance in countries like Germany that have a more decentralised spatial structure. Given the evidence of clustering advantages in certain country contexts, it can be expected that similar mechanisms draw NGOs to cluster in certain locations.

2.3.2 Main theories of NGO clustering motivations and their corresponding evidence

While a vast strand of literature has found NGOs to be influenced by ecological factors when deciding their location (Fruttero & Gauri 2005; Joassart-Marcelli & Wolch 2003; Nemenoff 2008; Peck 2008), other studies have linked an organisation's human resource potential and client profile when deciding locations (Pfeffer 1982; Scott 1999).

Similarly, to what has been found in the private sector, there are multiple frameworks that conceptualise clustering behaviours in the non-profit sector. According to MacLean (2015), the distribution of NGOs tends to be affected by

(1) a community's level of need for the service provided; (2) how convenient the location is for NGO staff and founders; and (3) the political environment for NGOs operating in the country. This dissertation will use this conceptual differentiation into three broad categories to conduct the Brazil-specific analysis. In their cross-country analysis of the dispersion of electricity NGOs in Africa, McLean et. Al (2015) finds that, despite widespread need, there is disproportionate concentration of such NGOs in a few countries, weakening the evidence for clustering according to the need-based hypothesis.

Multiple studies have come to contrasting conclusions about what predominant factor influences NGO clustering behaviours. While Nancy and Yontcheva (2006) state that NGOs are often believed to be more altruistic because they prioritise need over political and commercial interests, there has been considerable pushback against this "blanket statement". Brass (2012) in Kenya argues that both "saintly" and "self-serving" motivations play a role in NGO clustering, as they are mostly plotted based on need, but display a certain urban concentration that points to the importance of service provision infrastructure for clustering. Jammulamadaka & Varman (2010) in India find that assessed need is not a significant vehicle for NGO formation. Rather, it is more related to perceptions of need that are far removed from local realities of poverty, as evidenced by the fact that per capita income is positively correlated with Ngo formation. They also find that, while many organisations intend to locate based on need, they ultimately struggle and end up locating based on other criteria. Meanwhile, Mallick and Nabin (2018) argue that, based on microfinance institutions in 156 villages in northern Bangladesh, a strong commitment to a mission might be a good predictor for needs-based clustering, as they also find that NGOs with a broader humanitarian objectives place larger emphasis on poverty alleviation than NGOs with only a microfinance program.

They also find that microfinance institutions are more reluctant to cover more remote areas with less developed infrastructure, no marketplace and fewer localised marketing opportunities.

When it comes to the relevance of the so-called "self-serving motivation" of NGO clustering, there is a vast body of scholarship identifying a variety of relevant factors. Davis and Swiss (2020), for instance, argue that NGOs are more likely to operate in easier institutional environments, especially when they are relying on funding from governments, because continued funding is dependent on perceptions of success. The way in which a focus on satisfying short-term donor goals can compromise the pursuit of transformational development solutions was aptly demonstrated by Bebbington (2004), who found evidence that the Dutch government directed NGOs in the Peruvian and Bolivian Andes to demonstrate immediate poverty alleviation, meaning that it may have prevented more entrenched forms of poverty from being adequately addressed. In this context, Büthe, Major, & Souza (2012) have also found that risk-averse NGOs will often replicate country-based aid allocation of their back donors. Brass (2012) adds to this existing literature by finding that some of the factors

included in this self-serving motivation range from better access to infrastructure such as good roads, elite goods and benefitting from shared networks and resources with other NGOs. Moroto, Sakamoto and Ahmed (2018) report similar findings that disaster management NGOs in Bangladesh tends to locate disproportionately in more accessible rather than disaster-vulnerable areas. While projects were more concentrated in cyclone-prone areas, there was still a disproportionate number of urban organisations, with a particular bias towards proximity to airports. Thus, even though multiple surveyed NGOs expressed a strong commitment to locating in disaster-prone areas in their communication, they failed to deliver on that promise. Kareithi and Flisher (2008) in their study of HIV-related NGOs in South Africa, find that, while NGO activity suggests a strategic response to young people, a higher prevalence of service sites or offices in higher HIV prevalence areas has not been observed, which means that NG location isn't determined by HIV prevalence. The incentive for NGOs to locate where there are other NGOs has been confirmed by Davis and Swiss (2020), as they find that herding behaviour is the strongest predictor of NGO location.

It is important to note that many of the trends in clustering that have been identified at the national or subnational levels by previous researchers has also been confirmed by scholars in their multi-country analyses. By identifying global trends in unequal NGO clustering, these researchers add to the severity of the issue at hand. Koch et. al (2009) come to similar conclusions in their global analysis of 61 countries using a multivariate regression model to find that poverty plays a role in aid allocation but is not the only or even the main determinant. Although poorer countries are the main recipients of aid, factors such as familiar cultural ties, the preferences of backdonors and an already established Ngo sector will drive location choice. By doing this, it can be argued that NGos fall short in a very significant way, because they do not present an alternative or complement to the official aid allocation. A similar-global analysis of the inequalities of ties between international NGOs by Beckfield (2003) from 1960 to 2000 finds that there is a persistently high level of inequality in NGO ties at the level of world income inequality, with growing western domination over time. Zhou (2015) also conducts a zero-inflated negative binomial model to test the distribution of human rights transnational NGOs, finding an uneven distribution of 787 human rights organisations from the 2005 to the 2010 due to factors such as population size, political institutions, economic development, availability of human resources, education, strong democratic institutions, and less stringent regulatory environment. The study also finds that states can play an important role in influencing this clustering behaviour by providing a welcoming or repressive environment.

2.3.3 Clustering literature in developed country contexts

Considering that a lot of the factors influencing clustering decisions of NGOs regarding the self-interest motivation, such as clustering next to better infrastructure or elite goods, might be less prominent in developed countries, there is the theoretical possibility that NGOs might be better able to cluster according to need in developed countries. It is therefore interesting to note that the evidence for this is very much mixed. On one hand, Peck (2004) finds evidence of NGOs clustering primarily according to need in Phoenix (USA), Bütte et. al (2012) find that international development funds coming from the USA are also largely allocated based on need and Joassart-Marcellei & Giordano (2006) find evidence against the notion that NGO funds are primarily allocated to serve the survival or employment needs of the NGO itself.

On the other hand, there is a significantly larger body of research that frames clustering behaviours of developed-country NGos in a somewhat similar, if slightly more positive light compared to developing country NGos. Nemenoff (2008) finds that the number of NGOs in Kansas City (USA) were more likely to be located where

median income is higher and where there is more racial diversity. When there is less diversity, clustering is driven by higher income. Peck (2008) comes to slightly different conclusions for anti-poverty NGOs in the city of Phoenix, finding that they do locate to poorer areas, but not in a way that mirrors poverty estimates. Jossart-Marcelli and Wolch (2003) in Southern California find that non-profit spending rates decrease as poverty rates increase, but overall poverty is hardly correlated with non-profit activity. Allard (2004) finds that center city poor have greater access to services than those in suburbs and demographic changes do not necessarily match well to the location of service provision.

When it comes to international aid flows from developed countries, Dreher, Mölders & Nunnenkamp (2010) (as quoted by Davis & Swiss, 2020) challenge the notion that NGOs are better targeters of poverty by showing that official development assistance from state agencies in Sweden and Canada has a stronger anti-poverty orientation than funds targeted through NGOs. Aldashev, Marini and Verdier (2020), on the other hand, identify uneven distribution of NGO projects per sector and disproportionately high aid flows to 10 countries in their analysis of aid projects from OECD countries.

2.3.4 Political connectivity motivation

Despite the importance of need-based and convenience-based hypotheses of NGO clustering, it is important to also discuss the relevance of the hypothesis of politically motivated clustering. Here, it is again interesting to note that there appear to be significant advantages to fostering political relationships in the private sector. Political connections have been shown to make it easier for firms to take on more risk (Bliss & Gul, 2012), while firms that have a politician on the firm board tend to borrow more and default more (Khwaja & Mian, 2005). Houston et. al (2018) find that politically-connected U.S government contractors have lower cost of debt than non-connected contractors, while Amore and Bennedsen (2013) find that profitability of Danish firms connected to local politicians is greater than that of non-connected firms when doing business with the public sector. An analysis of corporate political connections in 47 countries by Fisman (2001) finds evidence of such connections in 35 of them.

Thus, given the importance of political connections for the granting of privileges and advantages to entities in the public sector, it is unsurprising that such relationships are also found between NGOs and governments. Harrison (2017) finds evidence for political connections being more relevant for budget allocation than adherence to a strong bureaucratic process in the Indian context, while Johnson and McGinnis (2015) do not find such a relationship for the Chinese context. However, Wang (2020) finds that politically connected NGOs report higher revenues from private donations and from government grants, though the activity area of the NGO does not appear to be relevant here. AbouAssi and Bowman (2018) find that personal and political connections are one of five defining features shaping relationships between local government and NGOs in the developing world. They find that previous professional interactions, informal kinship relationships and elite connections are more likely to lead to constructive NGO- government relationships, especially when they occur at the local level, since NGO staff and government staff might share the same social circles. In their study of Brazil, Lopez, Souza and Grangeia (2011) find that the importance of clientelistic relationships between the state and the third sector are diminishing.

Lewis (2008) and Lewis (2011) expand on the relevance of different forms of boundary-crossing for the establishment of relationships between NGOs and government. Based on findings in the UK, the Philippines and Bangladesh, boundary-crossing has become more common in the context of flexible organisational structures that become more common under neoliberal market arrangements. Lewis (2008) argues that boundary crossing

can be consecutive (move from one sector to the other) or extensive (hold positions in both sectors simultaneously). It is further argued that sector boundaries can be blurred by financial flows, familial ties, agents and alumni groups and social embeddedness of employees within wider communities. Boundary-crossing usually takes place in consecutive forms when 1) people opt to cross into a higher paying sector 2) People opt to cross due to career planning reasons, 3) opt to gain relevant experience, 4) motivation to work as a bridge-builder between two sectors. Extensive forms of boundary crossing: 1) role of personal relationships, importance of affective ties based on relation. 2) Political patronage 3) Kinship between people of similar sectors.

In a study of an Australian integrated community based domestic violence program based on co-location with a police station, Mundy and Seufert (2021) find that co-location initiatives between NGOs and law enforcement are positive because they improve safety and empowerment of survivors, police transparency and accountability. Researchers conducted 2-hour semi-structured interviews with 9 people who had been in contact with the service in the past. While the sample size is small and there is low external validity due to the program being very specific, it nevertheless shows the advantages that NGOs get from being near state infrastructure.

3 Methodology

In order to test to what extent, the need-based hypothesis explains NGO clustering trends in the Brazilian North, this research will follow a mixed-methods methodology consisting of regression analysis and semi-structured interviews in a methodology that resembles a simplified form of Brass (2012), Lopez et. al (2011) and Fruttero and Gauri (2005). Brass (2012), for instance, employs a linear regression estimate to evaluate the hypothesis of need-based NGO clustering and then supplements the quantitative analysis with multiple interviews with a variety of stakeholders (NGO workers, public servants, politicians and civil society members). Following an arguably frequent trend in the NGO clustering literature, this study also utilised a mixed-methods research design because, while the relevance of the needs-based hypothesis could be tested via a regression analysis using publicly-available data, the convenience-based hypothesis of NGO clustering can involve a multitude of factors that are best fleshed out qualitatively. Similarly, there are multiple facets of the political connectivity aspect that are best addressed through a private, semi-structured interview instead of an online survey or a focus group.

3.1 Quantitative Portion

Based on the literature reviewed, the following hypotheses to test need-based clustering would emerge:

H1- A higher number of education, health and environment sustainability-related non-profits relative to the population (outcome variable Y) will be found in a municipality where education, health and environmental conservation-related indexes (control variables X) are lower.

Data for the outcome variable (number of OSCIPs per municipality) has been extracted from two publicly-available databases of government organisations (the Institute of Applied Economic Research – IPEA and the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics -IBGE) containing both a nationwide OSCIP registry and a nationwide NGO registry. It is important to note here that, while this research originally intended to make a comparison between the quantity of sector-specific OSCIPs versus sector-specific NGOs to test whether their clustering patterns differ, the quantitative analysis is unfortunately limited to OSCIPs because the general NGO registry does not categorise NGOs by their activity sector, while the OSCIP registry does.

Data for the various control variables was gathered from an IPEA database of municipal literacy, school at-

tainment and school infrastructure data (for the education-related regressions), IPEA database on infant mortality rates and public health infrastructure (for the health-related regressions) and IPEA database on municipal “environmentalism” data, such as availability of clean water, plumbing, etc. It is important to note here that particularly the indexes pertaining to the environmentalism regression are sub-optimal measures and might be more related to infrastructure than environmental conservation. However, the research was conducted under some data constraints as, while more sophisticated data on municipal environmental criteria exists, such data exists for only a few municipalities that would not have yielded a large enough sample for a regression analysis to be possible.

There are four identified limitations in the current quantitative methodology:

- 1) As previously identified by Kareithi and Flisher (2009), absence of a time-series measurement of both the evolution of the quantity of NGOs over time and the evolution of associated indexes over time prevents observance of potential longitudinal shifts, thereby omitting potential reverse causality issues in the data. However, the time-series element was not present in the publicly-available data and attempts to gather it from the relevant public bodies went unanswered.
- 2) Considering that the municipal level is the smallest unit of analysis available when it comes to government data, regression results might obfuscate a potential clustering of NGOs in certain neighbourhoods. This is especially relevant when taking into consideration extreme social inequalities in large metropolitan areas.
- 3) Considering that the available databases on NGOs do not collect data on the quantity, location and size of projects run by the NGO, the data from this NGO registry might again be hiding a clustering process by project allocation or subsidiary location that cannot be accounted for in the current methodology, thereby creating the potential for measurement error issues in the data. Similar limitations were found in the research of Galway, Corbett and Zeng (2012).
- 4) Since a variety of public databases, compiled during various time periods were used for the compilation of this analysis, a possible relationship of correlation may be muddled due to the different time periods of data collection.

3.2 Qualitative Methodology

The qualitative section of the dissertation collected primary data in the form of semi-structured interviews with 18 NGO managers and founders in the state of Pará. Faced with the absence of a longitudinal analysis and the discrepancies data collection year for some of the government data used in the quantitative analysis, this portion will attempt to discern the extent to which NGO managers and figureheads perceive the organisation as having clustered based on need, self-interest, or political motivations. Harrison (2017) and Brass (2012) have also opted for a semi-structured interview methodology after noting important shortcomings in the existing, publicly-available data.

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First the interviewees were asked a series of fact-based questions about the NGO’s missions, activities, revenue sources, size, etc. Then, they were asked to rate the importance of several factors from 1 to 10 (1 being least important and 10 being most important) when choosing the location for their projects. Here, these factors reflected clustering motives based on perceived community need, convenience and political connectivity. While this method was chosen to create a numerical component that would allow comparisons, evaluations of motivations are subjective and how respondents will translate these perceptions into numerical values will also vary. Finally, respondents answered a series of questions about the principal motivations and

challenges surrounding the NGOs establishment, growth and service to the community. Here, questions of the political relationships between NGOs and government were not asked directly, but rather reflected in subjective evaluations regarding trends in the sector.

Thus, this section will have the following hypotheses:

H1 – NGOs will report a high motivation to cluster based on need and will consistently identify need as the most important clustering factor.

H2 – NGOs will report several convenience-based factors as the main factors for clustering.

H2b - Proximity to private and public donors will be most important given longstanding resource constrains in the sector.

H3 – NGOs will report advantages related to securing funding based on political relationships and will report these relationships as influencing their clustering choices. NGOs who have a history of relationships with the public sector and previous public sector employees will report political relationships as more important for clustering.

3.3 Methodological Trade-offs

Combining a quantitative methodology and the qualitative methodology allows the researcher to examine the contribution of other elements such as the perceived “popularity” of the issue that the NGO is catering to. Considering that part of the research examines the perceptions of motivations, desires and interests of human beings, a qualitative approach is more appropriate here and, a combination of the two allows for more complex mechanisms and concepts to be tested. At the same time, the current qualitative methodology only allows for inferences into the perceptions of participants in relation to the second and third theory.

At the same time, it is important to note that the qualitative methodology, specifically the semi-structured interview, has a number of potential drawbacks. According to Adams (2015), one major drawback of the SSI methodology is that “*SSI are unlikely to encompass a large enough sample to yield much precision in the estimate of the views of the population from which the sample was drawn*” (p.496). At the same time, this methodology also presents some key advantages that make it the best fit for this research design, such as the fact that this methodology is best suited for probing, open-ended questions that respondents might feel uncomfortable answering in a group setting or when one wishes to give interviewees “*maximum latitude to spot useful leads and explore them*” (ibid, 497). Both instances apply to the current design since information on financial flows and relationships with various stakeholders required private interviews.

Lastly, it is important to note that an important drawback in my methodology was the usage of 3 brokers. These people were NGO figureheads who I had approached at the beginning of my research with requests of recommending organisations for interviews following low response rates over email. Therefore, about 2/3 of the interviewed NGO managers and figureheads were part of the network of those previous interviewees. The fact that most interviews came about in this manner compromises the randomisation aspect and perhaps explains that many of the interviewed organisations fall outside the scope of the size, revenue, and staff number of the average Brazilian NGO.

4 Results

4.1 Results from quantitative analysis

As can be seen in the regressions performed below, while there is a high number of observations, the adjusted R Square value is low across the board for all three regressions, giving little evidence of a correlation between the variables.

SUMMARY OUTPUT - Regression of quantity of municipal health-related oscips and municipal health-related data								
Regression Statistics								
Multiple R		0,345113115						
R Square		0,119103062						
Adjusted R Square		0,094113078						
Standard Error		3,98942839						
Observations		146						
ANOVA								
		<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>		
Regression		4	303,415867	75,8539667	4,76603194	0,00123083		
Residual		141	2244,09098	15,9155389				
Total		145	2547,50685					
		<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95,0%</i> <i>Upper 95,0%</i>
Intercept		-7,692424142	27,8183947	-0,2765229	0,78255137	-62,687485	47,3026364	-62,687485 47,3026364
Infant mortality		0,142698871	0,33046043	0,43181833	0,66653305	-0,5105988	0,7959965	-0,5105988 0,7959965
Mortality under 5 y.o		-0,047446092	0,25954653	-0,1828038	0,85521455	-0,5605518	0,46565961	-0,5605518 0,46565961
HDI		8,740476965	29,6021391	0,29526505	0,76822576	-49,780924	67,261878	-49,780924 67,261878
Number of Doctors percapita		1,136098798	0,29175014	3,89408146	0,00015162	0,55932877	1,71286883	0,55932877 1,71286883

Source: OSC Portal

Based on the regressions below, it cannot be concluded that there is a correlation between municipal need and corresponding OSCIP activity on a national level.

SUMMARY OUTPUT - regression of municipal education-related data and quantity of education-related oscips per municipality.								
Regression Statistics								
Multiple R		0,415463981						
R Square		0,17261032						
Adjusted R Square		0,129063495						
Standard Error		8,297783486						
Observations		161						
ANOVA								
		<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>		
Regression		8	2183,35544	272,91943	3,96378654	0,00027442		
Residual		152	10465,688	68,8532108				
Total		160	12649,0435					
		<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95,0%</i> <i>Upper 95,0%</i>
Intercept		-14,65662757	22,5958293	-0,648643	0,51754789	-59,29907	29,9858151	-59,29907 29,9858151
meduca		2,710366905	2,80562604	0,9660471	0,33555513	-2,8326914	8,25342523	-2,8326914 8,25342523
t_med25m		-0,631941665	0,5369133	-1,1769901	0,24103923	-1,692718	0,42883468	-1,692718 0,42883468
t_fora4a5		-0,072110489	0,08304896	-0,8682889	0,38660506	-0,2361898	0,09196884	-0,2361898 0,09196884
t_fund25m		0,267386042	0,4925387	0,54287317	0,58801228	-0,7057197	1,24049175	-0,7057197 1,24049175
t_analf15m		0,250788805	0,38496957	0,65145098	0,51573914	-0,5097932	1,01137085	-0,5097932 1,01137085
t_fora6a14		1,663848108	0,92172033	1,80515505	0,07302964	-0,1571892	3,48488537	-0,1571892 3,48488537
t_super25m		0,683669866	0,34203729	1,99881673	0,04741107	0,00790886	1,35943087	0,00790886 1,35943087
i_freq_prop		-2,751373326	19,4841827	-0,1412106	0,88789054	-41,246155	35,743408	-41,246155 35,743408

SUMMARY OUTPUT - Regression of municipal environmental-related oscips and municipal environmental data								
Regression Statistics								
Multiple R	0,12820025							
R Square	0,0164353							
Adjusted R S	-0,0179186							
Standard Err	2,71186346							
Observations	119							
ANOVA								
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>			
Regression	4	14,1321509	3,53303772	0,64054755	0,63465298			
Residual	115	845,733395	7,35420344					
Total	119	859,865546						
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95,0%</i>	<i>Upper 95,0%</i>
Intercept	-4,2930246	9,68468396	-0,4432798	0,65839618	-23,47652	14,8904704	-23,47652	14,8904704
agua_esgotc	0,00253451	0,06656882	0,03807357	0,96969504	-0,1293255	0,13439453	-0,1293255	0,13439453
t_luz	0,02936548	0,08706746	0,33727266	0,73652616	-0,1430984	0,20182937	-0,1430984	0,20182937
t_sluz	0,03268819	0,03683219	0,88748983	0,3766676	-0,0402693	0,10564567	-0,0402693	0,10564567

4.2 Results from semi-structured interviews

When it comes to the profile of organisations interviewed, it must first be noted that they vary greatly in multiple aspects. While they were mostly located in the Pará state and were all in northern Brazil, they differ substantially in many demographic characteristics, their funding sources, and their reported relationships with government.

4.2.1 Demographic Characteristics and representativeness of sample

Demographic Characteristics of Interviewed Organisations		
Area of expertise	Sustainability	40%
	Membership orgs.	20%
	Civil rights causes	27%
	Education	7%
	Health	7%
Average years operating		37
% of oscips		23%
Staff number		AVG: 45,2
		STDEV: 59
Schooling of employees	High School	33%
	Complete Undergrad	33%
	Complete Postgrad	22%
	PHD/Postdoc	11%
Salaries		22% Unpaid
		Avg: R\$ 4.091

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As observed in the demographic characteristics of the organisation, they are predominantly sustainability and civil rights-based, which corresponds to national and local trends observed by IBGE (Lopez 2018). Similarly Lopes (2018) found that most of the largest institutions in terms of employment are health and education-related,

while the average employment of these organisations in the sample was 87.6, so considerably above the sample mean of 45,2. On the other hand, national third sector averages demonstrate that 90% of organisations only have up to 2 formal employees, which is significantly lower than in this sample. The organisations sampled also had significantly more educated staff compared to national NGO averages: While 66% of NGO employees nationally did not finish college, 49% finished high school and 14% middle school, in this sample 66% of organisations reported their average employee as having a college degree or higher. At the same time, average salary levels in this sample tend to be closer to national averages: The national average salary for someone with a university degree is R\$ 4.237, while the average salary in this research sample is R\$ 4.091. Finally, while most NGOs tend to not survive the 2-year mark, the average of years’ operating as NGOs in this sample is 37. Thus, it can be said that the average organisational profile of this sample is composed of organisations that are considerably larger, older, with more formal employment and more educated staff. At the same time, salaries do not appear to be significantly different from national averages, which is probably driven by the fact that salaries in Pará, one of Brazil’s poorest states, are significantly lower than the Brazilian average.

4.2.2 Interviewee Profile

Interviewee Profile		
Position	President or Director	83%
	Regional Manager	11%
	Consultant	6%
Compensation	Unpaid	39%
	Paid	61%
other occupation	Public sector	22%
	Consultancy	22%
	Private sector	28%
	Academia	17%
	No other occupation	22%
Correlation between education and work?	Unspecified other	17%
	Yes	83%
Schooling	No	17%
	High school	17%
	Bachelors	39%
Past public sector experience	Masters	44%
	Yes	67%
	No	33%

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As evidenced by the interviewee profile, the great majority of interviewees were in paid upper management positions with previous public sector experience. While there is considerable variation in the occupation’s interviewees report having, 78% of interviewees report having another source of income. Also, while boundary-crossing was identified between the third and public sector (22%), the highest amount of boundary-crossing is found in the private sector (28%). Thus, it can be said that the nature of boundary-crossing in the sample of NGOs is extensive rather than consecutive, as most organisations report having had public sector experience than are currently employed in the public sector.

4.2.4 Revenues and funding sources

On the topic of average revenues, it is important to mention that two very large outliers (one NGO with a revenue of in the 8 figures and one company with a revenue of zero) were excluded from the calculation of the average and standard deviation. Still, the standard deviation remains very high (average revenue is 1.2 Mil and STD is 900k), denoting stark inequalities in the financial structures of each organisation, which reflect their size, employee number, branch structure, etc.

When it comes to the sources of revenues themselves, they tend to be predominantly derived from the sale of own goods and services and donations by private persons and corporations. While government resources are also significant, the importance of the private sector as a funding source and the sale of the NGO’s own goods and services is in line with shifting trends in funding sources across Latin America as highlighted by Pousadela & Cruz (2016) and others.

Financial Characteristics of Interviewed Organisations			
Annual revenues		Avg: R\$ 11 M	
		Std: 31 Mil	
Number subsidiaries		No subsidiaries: 65%	
		1 subsidiary: 15%	
		Remaining 20% ranged from 13 to 5,000 subsidiaries	
Main revenue sources	Sales of goods and services		55%
	Private Person donations		44%
	Corporate donations		39%
	Government Transfers	Municipal	11%
		State	16%
		Federal	22%
	Membership fees		17%
	Foundations		11%
owner's contributions		6%	
other - unspecified		11%	
Urban/Rural breakdown	Predominantly Metropolitan		44%
	Predominantly Rural		17%
	Evenly spread		39%
Info National Public sector revenues		28% received public sector revenue	
Revenues predominantly urban?		92% said yes.	
Changes in financial fluxes from the state?		Yes	

On the changes in financial fluxes from the state, while a significant portion of organisations did not answer this question, the five organisations that did have confirmed that revenues from state transfers decreased significantly over the years, attributing this to disclosure and compliance measures having become more stringent.

4.2.5 Results of Clustering Motivation Questions

Two important insights emerge from the portion of the interview that asked participants to assign a numerical value to their clustering motivations:

Clustering according to a need identification and proximity to the interest community was a dominant expressed motive for NGOs, while proximity to the owner/staff’s local community was ranked as relatively low, emphasising a widespread commitment to cluster based on need instead of self-interest, at least in theory.

While some factors are more relevant than others, all averages had correspondingly-high standard deviations,

denoting a diversity of opinion that mirrors diversity in terms of demographics. Given that the majority of organisations have a private-sector orientation in their funding strategies, it is expected that some top-ranked factors are proximity to private donors and preferential access to financial resources from firms. Also, going by the largest standard deviations, it can be said that the most “polarising” issues are the proximity to public donors and coordination with other NGOs.

Category	Average	STDEV
Management importance	8,42	2,15
Need identification	8,36	2,27
Proximity	Prox.Loc.Comm	4,86
	Comm. Of int.	8,14
	Labour market	4,62
	Urban	6,29
	Infrastructure	6,93
	Private Donors	7,29
	Public Donors	4,71
Maintenance costs	4,77	
Ease of organising	6,82	
Contacts with public bodies	6,50	
Access to financing	GOvernment	5,64
	Private Persons	4,38
	Firms	6,21
	Foundations etc.	3,79
Presence of other Ngos	4,57	
Presence of Ngos - Same Sector	4,14	

While a majority of respondents see an urban concentration in the origin of their revenues, many accordingly reported needing to set up an infrastructure in metropolitan areas (such as renting an office space or hiring a dedicated employee). 3 respondents reported that having an office in an urban area was a primary concern for fundraising with private donors.

The importance of management in fundraising is a surprising effect considering how consistently it is rated relatively high regardless of size of organisation or revenue. It would have been expected that managerial protagonism would be bigger in smaller organisations and that larger orgs would have a less centralised structure for revenue mobilisation.

4.2.6 Reported Challenges in project expansion

When asked what issues prevent them from targeting needs effectively in their project expansion, virtually all organisations reported resource constraints as their chief concern. Lack of transport infrastructure and human capital- related challenges in the context of labour markets were also dominant themes. For those organisations that rely predominantly on public funds, the main constraint for project expansion was navigating public bureaucracy, with only one organisation highlighting meddling by public bodies as a chief concern. Infrastructure issues appeared to be more relevant for organisations with less available funding, presumably because adequate funding can overcome the cost associated with having to rely on poor public infrastructure. While proximity to the private and public sectors was important for project expansion, there was less of a reported need to establish infrastructure in urban settings when targeting public donors, in which case proximate

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personal relationships and networking become more relevant. While NGOs were fairly evenly-split on whether they consider their resource mobilisation as happening more in higher education or wealthier areas, 2/3 of those who found increased concentration in urban areas reported issues of infrastructure and low human capital as the main constraints to expanding resource mobilisation outside of urban areas.

When it comes to the relationships that third sector organisations have with each other, they seem to be characterised by a certain indifference. While few organisations viewed the presence or absence of other organisations as a concern for clustering decisions, they also do not appear to take other organisations into account when expanding their projects. Yet still, a majority of respondents (64%) believed that relationships between NGOs were collaborative, while only 7% argued they are competition-based and 21% argued they were neither collaborative nor competition-based. Most respondents do not find that other NGOs play a role in clustering, regardless of whether activities are similar (42%) or different (35%), against 14% who do find that NGOs in general affect their clustering choices and similar NGOs even more 21%.

On the effect that private sector preferences will have on the kinds of services and programs the NGO develops, it is important to note firstly that there was an overall low response rate to this question, as only 21% of respondents chose to answer. The organisations more willing to readily admit a direct influence of private donors on their clustering behaviour are those non-profits and membership associations that directly cater to the private sector (such small special interest associations collecting membership fees). One organisation that caters to a wide variety of demographics indicated that “emphasising service expansion to cater to the needs of children was perceived as a more effective than explicitly attempting to cater to other demographics perceived as less sympathetic”. Still, 50% of respondents did not perceive these concerns to be of relevance for their clustering behaviour, some due to relying predominantly on public funds, but a significant portion of respondents manifested a lack of interest of the private sector in the activities of the NGO. Here, the dominant themes were both an expressed view that, contrary to what happens in other countries, in Brazil private persons and the private sector more generally are not receptive to NGO needs and a culture of charitable giving does not exist to the same extent.

On marketing: While 28% of respondents did not answer this question, those organisations who did not find marketing relevant to their resource mobilisation operations were the ones who relied predominantly on public funds. All other organisations found it important, even if they reported not being able to dedicate themselves to this goal fully.

4.2.7 Public sector relationships:

It is interesting to note here that, while a few respondents declined to answer or did not know how to answer previous questions, there was a consistent, higher rate of no answers to these specific questions. Lack of response to these questions always ranged between 20-30% of interviewees.

When discussing their general relationship with the state, organisations varied a lot. While those who did manifest a good relationship with the state discussed their proximity to politicians or members of government bodies, none of them highlighted relationships with local bureaucrats themselves, even the organisations who receive public funds through government bureaucracy. On the other hand, those who reported a negative relationship either did so because they would like to form relationships and perceive themselves as being ignored by the state, whereas others forgo state relationships completely, citing corruption and meddling.

When it comes to the likelihood of NGO- public sector relationships, three respondents felt that such relationships are not frequent or important for organisations similar to their own. All other respondents felt that a big

incentive exists to cultivate relationships to communicate issues to bureaucrats or to engage in lobbying with politicians. One organisation mentioned that in their sector relationships with the state can generate advantages in the public procurement process.

When asked if organisations receiving public funds have higher incentives to cultivate relationships with bureaucrats and politicians, all organisations but one felt that there is a bigger chance of such relationships forming. While four respondents chose to highlight the ways in which recent legal changes have made these relationships more transparent and formalised, one respondent argued that the nature of funding permanently alters relationships between government and NGOs because they abandon their civil society role to become executors of the state agenda. It was also noted that these relationships will inevitably lead to the adoption of less “radical” positions by NGOs.

When it was asked whether respondents believed that there are certain regions where access to public and private funds is easier, responses typically reflected the idea that funding was more easily available in the south and south-east of Brazil due to state- third sector relationships being overwhelmingly tense. When the same question was asked with a focus on the private sector, responses highlighting a perceived greater openness of the private sector in the South and South-East to give donations to NGOs.

When it comes to the factors that respondents believed to be more closely associated with organisations gaining access to public resources, over 50% of respondents believed it to be the quality of work, followed by acting in specific areas (noting the importance of embracing less polarising issues), while previous work experience with local communities and contacts with politicians were tied in third place. While this demonstrates a general focus on quality of work and experience, it also points towards the idea that the government will be more likely to fund specific projects and that contacts to politicians are important. It is interesting to note here that 28% of respondents picked contacts with politicians while only 22% picked contacts with local bureaucracy. Similar to the last question, the predominant answers focused on quality of work, an established reputation within the sector and past work experience with local community. When it comes to the private sector, the answer to the question is relatively similar, focusing on quality of work, an established reputation within the sector and past work experience with the local community.

Finally, when exploring the negative side of political relationships, most respondents highlighted a fear of excessive meddling by the public body in the everyday dealings of the organisation, though many respondents did not answer this question. Many more identified a lack of political connections as an impediment when trying to access funds. The 3 respondents who answered the question about the privileged information found that all factors are relevant.

5 Discussion

Based on evidence in Harrison et. al (2017), Lewis (2008; 2011) and Abou-Assi and Bowman (2018) the highly personalised nature of NGOs and boundary crossing may generate personal relationships and improve access to funding. Based on the relatively high score of management importance for funding and the high levels of boundary-crossing identified particularly in the private sector, this might explain why most NGOs rely more on private sector funding and report a more ambiguous relationship with the public sector. AbouAssi and Bowman (2018) find that informal kinship relationships as well as previous professional interactions are likely to lead to better relationships.

Based on some discrepancies in the answers provided in the clustering motivation rankings and the open-ended questions about project expansion challenges, it can be argued that, while NGOs are aware of several structural

factors that make clustering based on need more difficult and have developed strategies to curb said difficulties, they do not appear to view these factors as deciding factors for location choice “ex ante”. Therefore, they still report very high motivation to cluster based on need but encounter challenges that make their de-facto clustering choices seem more interest-based. Thus, while NGOs appear to express a genuine desire to cluster based on need identification, they ultimately struggle to live up to that promise and fail to do so in the same vein of what was reported by Jammulamadaka & Varman (2010) in India.

Considering that multiple NGOs in the sample reported the significance of infrastructure and proximity of private donors, they confirm previous findings by Brass (2012), Mallick & Nabin (2018) and Moroto, Sakamoto & Ahmed (2018) that infrastructure problems will represent a key impediment to the realisation of the need-based clustering motivation. Considering that the studies above (particularly Moroto, Sakamoto & Ahmed, 2018) found evidence of a commitment to need that is replicated in official documents, their findings are also similar to this study in the sense that it was found here that a motivation to cluster based on need is woven into the organisational narratives of the NGOs. Thus, this study is more in line with a strand of scholarship that views NGOs as well intentioned, if ineffective as opposed to outright opportunistic. For instance, while Barr and Fefchamps (2006) find that there is a general lack of willingness of NGOs to have a permanent presence in poorer communities, the sample of organisations interviewed does not support a clear tendency because, even though the majority of respondents agreed that revenues are urban, a significant portion of organisations also argued that activities are evenly spread and some even argued they were predominantly rural.

While some authors, like Malleck and Nabin (2018) argue that a strong theoretical commitment to a mission can be a predictor of need-based clustering, the fact that statistical analysis did not find a clear indication of such clustering could also be a consequence of the fact that 1) NGOs are failing to effectively coordinate their activities with other NGOs to avoid needless replication or 2) Perceived need by NGOs does not mirror actual need, as observed by Jammulamadaka & Varman (2010). It is interesting to point out here one specific answer to the question of the influence of other NGOs in location choice: When asked about the relevance of the presence of other NGOs in the location, the respondent said that that, as long as they identify a community in need, they will make an effort to locate there regardless of whether other NGOs are there and what they are doing. Based on this answer, it could be in their pursuit of targeting based on need while dealing with a myriad of constraints, many NGOs are forgetting to look at their surroundings with care to identify when their services might not be needed, but also to spot opportunities for collaboration with other NGOs.

While one could argue that the main problem plaguing NGOs today is the absence of resources, one must also consider the possibility that NGOs are fundamentally unable to rise to the occasion. In other words, there is a possibility that third sector enthusiasts must contend with the possibility that NGOs are unable to adequately identify, target and address need.

Relevance of political relationships

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It is also important to note that, while there is considerable heterogeneity in Ngo relationships with the government, the evidence points at these relationships being overwhelmingly sought after in largely legitimate ways. Based on the respondent’s impressions of their public sector relationships, it can be said that they vary greatly based on each organisation, but the dominant perception of the state is one of lack of collaboration. It is also striking that so many respondents perceived their relationships with government as more tense than in other regions and that the state is less willing to give access to funding sources in the North.

By pointing out these underlying tensions, respondents mirrored findings by Bratton (1989) in Kenya, who found that there are underlying tensions between NGOs and government, where NGOs seek to exercise autonomy and the government will exercise control. Given the known resource constrains the NGO sector is under, the steadily-decreasing government funds over the last decade, especially for NGOs in the North, could be seen as a form of exercising control. Having a disengaged relationship with NGOs in the context of these resource constrains might be a way of forcing compliance via institutional inertia.

At the same time, while organisations did express that certain types of projects may get preferential treatment over others, they did overall characterise government-NGO relationships as being predominantly performance and experience-based, even finding that positive NGO- government relationships can lead to credibility gains in host communities. Harrison et. al (2017) also finds that government relationships can lead to gained credibility. While some did find that government meddling might be an undesirable side effect of a relationship with the state, as also found by Harrison et. al (2017), a significantly larger portion of interviewees believed that a lack of relationship with the state is more negative.

Thus, while NGO figureheads have discussed that contact with government can be beneficial and have, to a much smaller extent, indicated that rent-seeking behaviour still happen, the government-NGO relationship found here corroborates the findings of Lopez et. Al (2011) for NGO-public sector in Brazil finding that relationships based on transparency and professional standards are increasing and clientelistic practices are increasingly falling out of favour. In this context, it must be said that, while relationships with the public sector will affect clustering decisions by NGOs to the extent that they might seek to be closer to these sources of funding, these relationships cannot be characterised as involving unethical behaviours in any real sense.

Given what has been previously discussed, we can accept H1 (NGOs reporting high motivation to cluster based on need and identifying it as the key factor), while rejecting H2 (NGOs identifying convenience-based factors as the most important generally and proximity to public and private donors specifically), since convenience-based factors were not the highest-rated and rejecting H2b since the the most highly-ranked convenience factors were infrastructure and private donors, not private and public donors. Finally, H3 (NGOs reporting political relationships as influencing their clustering choices) is more subjective due to the fact that, while political relationships represent an advantage that will motivate some NGOs to seek them out, this is not a unanimous finding and NGOs have not reported considering the public sector a main factor in clustering.

Concluding comments

This research project has studied clustering behaviours of Brazilian NGOs in the state of Pará, finding little quantitative evidence to support clustering based on objective need, but finding a strong ideological commitment to need-targeting by NGO figureheads. While they report a strong desire to cluster based on identified need, they are ultimately faced with significant resource constrains, infrastructure issues and labour market issues. In this context, they might seek closer ties to governments in order to secure funding, but there is little evidence of unethical behaviours.

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This research has contributed to the already vast literature on NGO location choice by conducting a study of NGO location choice in Brazil considering that no such study has been identified in Brazilian scholarship.

When taking into account the socio-political commonalities between Brazil and various other Latin American countries, it is unsurprising that the same shifts Brazilian NGOs have had to adapt to have also been identified in the whole of Latin America. Therefore, while the study itself is quite specific to the north of Brazil, similarities between Brazil and other Latin American countries might increase its external validity.

Furthermore, it should be noted that, while this study addressed the three main theories on NGO clustering and engaged with a variety of different factors (especially when it comes to the arguably most broad category, the self-interest motivation), some aspects have inevitably remained unaddressed. For instance, Kareithi & Flisher (2008) argue security is a significant concern for location choice, while Champion (2002) finds that employee motivation will also play a role in NGO location choice. While the inclusion of such elements would be relevant for the Brazilian context (specifically the security dimension given Brazil's high crime rates), a decision was made to stop including further dimension into the interviews to avoid them becoming too long and cumbersome for the interviewees. Furthermore, Büthe (2012) includes a distinction between a humanitarian (or needs-based) motive and a development motive in their analysis. The development motive would see NGO targeting interventions according to the development potential of the project, which is quite different than targeting need purely. This is again a fascinating dimension to location choice that future research in Brazil specifically and in Latin America generally should account for.

This study also finds significant implications for future research. The debate on the NGO's ability adequately target need will inevitably feed into the wider discussion on how NGO- state relationships should occur and whether it is advisable for the state to become the protagonist in public service provision. While current trends are unlikely to be completely reversed and NGO- state partnerships are here to stay, at the very least the discussion around NGO need targeting should motivate us to exercise caution when outsourcing state responsibilities to the third sector.

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Appendix - Translated Interview Questions

1) Questions directed at managers of NGOs/OS/OSCIPS/FOUNDATIONS

- a. What is your position within the organization? Is your work voluntary or paid? –
- b. Do you have another job outside of this organisation? If yes, which one?
- c. What is your education level?
 - i. Secondary/middle school
 - ii. Some GCSE, A-Levels/ High School
 - iii. Completed GCSE, A-Levels/ High School
 - iv. Some University – Undergraduate
 - v. Completed Undergraduate
 - vi. Postgraduate/Masters/PhD
- d. Do you consider your professional experience to be related to your current work in the organization? If so, briefly describe the professional experiences you think are relevant.
- e. What are your responsibilities in the organisation?
 - i. Everyday management (hiring, firing, payments, accounting, etc.)
 - ii. Reporting to public oversight bodies
 - iii. Project management of partnerships between the organization and the State.
 - iv. Organization of other products/services that are not subject to a partnership agreement.
 - v. Securing and expanding funding through private or public means.
 - vi. Others?
- f. Do you have past work experience in the public sector? If yes:
 - i. Which public body was it?
 - ii. What was your position?
 - iii. What was your responsibility?
- g. What are the main demographic characteristics of your organization?
 - i. Occupation area
 - ii. Time since organisation was founded.
 - iii. If you are an OSCIP, what year were you accredited?
 - iv. Number of branches/units and their location.
 - v. Number of employees.
 - vi. Average level of education of employees.
 - vii. Average salary level of employees.
- h. Do your organization's projects take place in one main community or in multiple simultaneous locations? Would you say there is a preference for urban areas?
 - i. What Is the average yearly revenue of the organisation?
 - j. What are the main revenue sources of the organisation ?
 - i. Municipal government transfers
 - ii. State government transfers
 - iii. Federal government transfers
 - iv. Transfers from international institutions
 - v. Transfers from foreign governments
 - vi. Sale of products and services
 - vii. NGO's own events/campaigns
 - viii. Donations from private persons
 - ix. Corporate donations
 - x. Others
 - k. If you have received resources from the government between 2010 and 2020 (or between the organization's founding year and 2020, if more recent):
 - i. How much do these revenues represent in relation to alternative sources of income?
 - ii. If it is an OSCIP, how many partnership terms were carried out per year from 2010 to 2020?
 - iii. Were these resources obtained through parliamentary amendments? If so, how much do these resources represent

in relation to the total?

- iv. Which level of government were these resources obtained from? (Federal/State/Municipal)
- v. Have you identified changes in financial flows from the government in recent years? (e.g Have they increased/decreased? Have they become more difficult/easy to obtain? Are they coming more from a specific entity of the federation? Have these transfers come more from parliamentary amendments?)
- vi. How was this grant awarded? Did this process come from the organization or from the public authorities?

2) Questions about motivation, location and importance of financial resources

a. What is your assessment of the importance of the organization's founders/managers in the search for financial resources? Select a number from 1 to 10, with 1 being unimportant and 10 essential.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

b. Speaking of your current position or of your overall experience in the third sector, when thinking of the factors that motivate an NGO to choose a certain location for establishment or expansion of its activities, please evaluate the relative importance of each of the factors below from 1(unimportant) to 10 (fundamental):

i. Identification of problems and needs of communities

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

ii. Proximity to the home/community of NGO management and staff

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

iii. Proximity to the community of interest / group of people to be impacted by the work of the organisation.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

iv. Proximity to a more attractive labour market/talent pool (advantages such as cheaper labour, more human capital, etc.)

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

v. Proximity to urban centres

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

vi. Access to better public and private infrastructure, such as health, education and security services.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

vii. Resource mobilisation: Proximity to private donors, such as foundations, institutes, companies and private persons.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

viii. Resource mobilisation: Proximity to public donors such as development banks, local, state and federal government funds, etc.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

ix. Lower maintenance costs for the organisation

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

x. Ease of organising and form associations with like-minded people.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

xi. Contacts with the relevant public bodies

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

xii. Easier access to funding due to contacts with bureaucracy (municipal/state secretariats, civil servants of relevant bodies)

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

xiii. Easier access to resources from donations of private persons.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

xiv. Easier access to corporate donations.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

xv. Easier access to donations by foundations and other donor organisations.

01, 02, 03, 04, 05, 06, 07, 08, 09, 10

xvi. The presence of a large number of third-sector organisations in the community of interest.
() 01, () 02, () 03, () 04, () 05, () 06, () 07, () 08, () 09, () 10

xvii. The presence of other third-sector organisations that pursue similar goals as your own in the community
() 01, () 02, () 03, () 04, () 05, () 06, () 07, () 08, () 09, () 10

c. How was your organization founded? Was the organisation established as a response to observed need or was it established through external interference? Which needs were identified? Are the organisation's founders linked to the community being targeted?

d. Are most of the funding sources of your organisation located in urban areas?
Establish importance of clustering in urban areas to check whether they

e. Does the expansion of projects usually occur in higher education areas?

f. What are the main difficulties your organization faces in expanding its activities?

g. To what extent does the existence or absence of infrastructure facilitate/complicate your organisation's work?

h. What is the relevance of proximity to a more interesting labor market (advantages such as cheaper, more qualified labor, greater intellectual capital)?

i. When it comes to fundraising, is proximity to private and public donors a factor that motivates the expansion of projects or establishment of organizations?

3) Questions about the relationship with other organisations and the public sector

a. In general terms, how would you describe your organisation's relationship with government?

b. How would you describe your organisation's relationship with its direct competitors? When speaking of your overall experiences in the Ngo sector, would you describe these relationships as being more collaborative or competitive?

c. Thus, would the presence of similar third sector organisations act as a deterrent or an incentive for an NGO to establish itself in a given community?

d. When defining project locations or expanding organisational activities, what is the importance of private donor preferences? Do you consider that some issues/areas/concerns attract a disproportionate amount of private donations?

e. What is the importance of marketing for the financing and resource mobilisation model of the organisation?

f. In your experience, what are the chances that organisations similar to yours will maintain relationships with the public sector?

g. Do you believe that NGOs receiving public funds have greater incentives to foster relationships with the local bureaucracy specifically and the public sector generally?

h. Do you believe that there are some places where the process of raising public funds is easier or more difficult? What factors do you believe are relevant to facilitate/hinder this process?

i. Do you believe that there are some places where the private fundraising process is easier or more difficult? What factors do you believe are relevant to facilitate/hinder this process?

j. In your opinion, what is the main advantage for organizations like yours to cultivate relations with public authorities?

i. Gaining credibility with the local community by leveraging trust in government oversight

ii. Knowledge exchanges between public authorities and non-profit organizations.

iii. Consolidating the organization's reputation with the public authorities

iv. Gaining credibility with the local community through the services of the organisation.

k. In your opinion, what are the main factors that facilitate organizations to receive access to public resources?

i. Quality of work

ii. Experience in the organization's industry

iii. Past work experience with the local community

iv. Acting in certain specific areas (that is, are there some activities that are more prone to receiving government funds?)

- v. Experience with local government agencies
- vi. Geographical proximity to public bodies. Which?
 - i. Municipal secretariats
 - ii. City Halls
 - iii. Agencies linked to the state government
 - iv. Agencies linked to the federal government
- vii. Geographical proximity to beneficiary communities
- viii. Size/structure of the organization
- ix. Contacts with development bank employees
- x. Contacts with public servants
- xi. Contacts with politicians:
 - l. In your opinion, what are the main factors that contribute to organizations receiving access to private resources?
 - i. Quality of work
 - ii. Experience in the organization's industry
 - iii. Past work experience with the local community
 - iv. Past work experience in an institution / private company
 - v. Geographical proximity to business centers
 - vi. Geographical proximity to urban centers in general
 - vii. Geographical proximity to beneficiary communities
 - viii. Size/structure of the organization
 - ix. Work in certain specific areas (ie are there some areas of work that private donors tend to favor more than others?)
 - x. Contacts with employees of private companies/foundations.
 - xi. Contacts with owners/managers of these organizations
- m. Do political connections have the potential to be harmful? In what way?
 - i. Exacerbated interference by the government in the organization's work.
 - ii. Alienation of organizations or people of different political orientation.
 - iii. Others
- n. Can the lack of political connections affect an organisation negatively? If so, how?
- o. Do you consider that managers of non-profit organizations gain access to privileged information through contact with the local bureaucracy? Which?
 - i. Volume of resources made available
 - ii. Areas in which these resources are available
 - iii. Assistance in project preparation
 - iv. Preference when selecting to enter into partnership terms
 - v. Access to confidential information about project approval/accountability status

4) Questions about the nature of the flow of financial resources:

- We realized that there is a large amount of associations and foundations in Pará, but few OSCIPs and OS compared to the south and southeast. In your opinion, why is this happening?
- It was found that there is no strong correlation between specific indexes that measure the performance of a particular municipality in a particular area of activity and the number of OSCIPs/NGOs operating in that area in that municipality. How would you explain this fact?
- We realized that there is a relationship between the number of OSCIPs in the North and the amount of municipal expenses. This correlation was found only in the North. Do you believe that there are certain municipalities that facilitate the release of funds to NGOs and OSCIPs? If yes, why?